

Insect resistance

Reaction of rice cultivars to pink stem borer (PSB)

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In 1981 kharif we screened 84 rices for reaction to PSB *Sesamia inferens* in the field at Hawalbagh, Almora, where the pest is endemic. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted, 2 plants/hill at 20- × 10-cm spacing in 2-row plots 2.5 m long.

Test varieties selected were stem borer-resistant and tolerant entries from various national and international nurs-

eries that were screened at Hawalbagh in 1980. VL 8 and China 1039 were the resistant and susceptible checks.

Pest incidence was heavy from Sep-Oct to panicle bearing. Whiteheads caused by stem tunnelling were counted at peak incidence on 10 hills of each variety, 75-80 d after transplanting. Cultivars were scored as resistant (0-5% infestation), moderately resistant (5.1-10%), susceptible (10.1-25%), and highly susceptible (above 25%).

Eight cultivars were resistant and 11 were moderately resistant. The rest were susceptible or highly susceptible (see table). □

Varietal resistance to PSB, Hawalbagh, India.

Reaction	Cultivars
Resistant (0-5%)	HPU803, HPU2199, IR9129-192-24-3, IR9758-150-3, IR19774-34-2-1, KAU 2110, VRS163-2-3, VRS291-3-1, VL8 (resistant check)
Moderately resistant (5.1-10%)	ARC11981, Fuzi 102, IR2053-521-1-1, IR7167-33-2-5, IR9129-263-3-3-2-3, IR9782-111-2-1, IRAT102, K228-8-3, K427, VRS245-2-1, VRS598-3-1

Genetics of resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in two rices

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath causes serious damage in Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, and Punjab. The insect lives with brown planthopper (BPH) at the base of rice plants and causes hopperburn.

We studied the genetics of resistance to WBPH in two resistant varieties: Balamawee and ARC10464. The two were crossed with susceptible TN1. Balamawee and ARC10464 also were crossed to learn the allelic relationship of the resistance

genes. The F₁ and F₂ populations were evaluated for WBPH reaction by bulk screening (see table)

Resistance in each of Balamawee and ARC10464 is governed by a single recessive gene. In both the crosses with TN1, the F₁ plants were susceptible and

the F₂ plants segregated as 3 susceptible: 1 resistant. In the cross Balamawee/ARC10464, the F₁ plants were susceptible and the F₂ segregated as 9 susceptible: 7 resistant, indicating that the recessive genes for resistance in both varieties are nonallelic. □

Reaction^a of F₁ and F₂ populations to WBPH, Pantnagar, India.

Cross	F ₁ reaction	Total (no.)	F ₂ reaction			X ²	P value
			R (no.)	S (no.)	Assumed genetic ratio		
TN1/Balamawee	S	137	39	98	1:3	0.88	0.50-0.30
TN1/ARC10464	S	136	40	96	1:3	1.41	0.30-0.20
Balamawee/ARC10464	S	189	77	112	7:9	0.56	0.50-0.30

^aS = susceptible, R = resistant.

Promising gall midge (GM) resistant rices with short to medium duration

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In the northern Telangana region of Andhra Pradesh, uncertain monsoon

conditions delay rice planting and crops suffer severe GM infestation. GM damage is particularly serious in Sep and Oct when there are high rainfall and humidity and many cloudy days.

We sought to develop 110- to 140-d varieties with GM resistance. Following are some popular GM-resistant varieties developed at ARS.

Surekha (IR8/Siam 29) is 80 cm tall with dark green foliage and erect leaves. It has 130- to 135-d duration and is suitable only for the monsoon season. It is lodging resistant, fertilizer responsive, and can be planted in late Jul. If planted late, 10- × 10-cm spacing is recommended. Each panicle has about 170 long, slender, translucent grains. Seed